

Has the acceptance of new technology a positive effect when it prevents a bad cause?

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ABSTRACT

Artificial intelligence (AI) is an emerging technology and has some major opportunities for organizations. Moreover, financial institutes are experimenting with artificial intelligence. The purpose of this study is to investigate the effects of new technology such as AI and the acceptance of this technology. In this research AI is used within financial banks that use private information to prevent money laundering or fraud as a case study for new technology. Two types of data collection are used to collect data about the acceptance of new technologies while using private information. The results imply that the relationship between the use of personal information and preventing money laundering or fraud, is of major influence towards accepting of artificial intelligence. This should be considered when financials institutes definitive introduce new technology to customers.

Keywords

Money laundering, artificial intelligence, business intelligence, predictive analytics, private financial information.

PROBLEM INTRODUCTION

In the early 21st century, a series of money-laundering cases in Europe were in the news. The latest addition to this case is the Dutch Central Bank that has started an investigation at ABN Amro because they suspect them of money laundering and finance of terrorism. These suspicions came from the fact that ABN Amro had not mentioned unusual transactions within their system for a long period. Furthermore, they suspect that clients of ABN Amro were not sufficiently investigated (Bloomberg, 2019). The eventual consequences of this case is a possible fine with a maximum of €450 million (Het Financieele Dagblad, 2019). To prevent this problem in the future, five of the largest Dutch banks

are exploring jointly monitoring transactions in the fight against money laundering (Bloomberg, 2019). The banks will investigate if a joint venture is achievable since there are technical and legal challenges involved, e.g. sharing of private information. According to the chief technology officer at ABN Amro, the banks are investigating to build algorithms and other new technologies to recognize suspicious activities (Bloomberg, 2019).

PROBLEM STATEMENT

Fraud detection involves monitoring the behavior of users in order to estimate, detect, or avoid undesirable behavior. There are multiple algorithms that detect credit card fraud. They are artificial neural-network models which are based upon artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning approach (Raj & Portia, 2011). In 2004, almost half of the world's top twenty financial banks are using AI systems, and AI has emerged as the leading method in the fight against money laundering (Kingdon, 2004). A study by Xurui Lui et al. (2017) showed new improving ways for AI against money laundering and fraud. Hence, AI was implemented early in the 21st century and currently it is being improved for optimal use as in cases like for money laundering.

Disruptive emerging technologies will play a major role in reshaping business models as they change the economics of all organizations. Gartner (2019) asked Chief Information Officers (CIOs) and IT leaders which technologies they expect to be most disruptive and AI was by far the most mentioned technology, therefore taking the spot as the top game-changer technology. As result we see that for making these analyses private information of customers is used.

AI is an emerging technology which is used in different activities and for different problem solving. With understanding new technology comes new technology readiness and technology acceptance. The results of a study by Godoe & Johansen (2012) showed that, when introducing new technology,

considerable emphasis should be placed on users and their general attitudes toward technology, especially in settings where it may be impractical to test the system before it is adopted. When general knowledge about users has been obtained, necessary steps could be taken to initiate successful implementations. A study by Adams et al. (1992) showed that financial banks are using technology for preventing money laundering or fraud and that when a new technology his perceived usefulness is high people tend to have a positive general attitude to it (Godoe & Johansen, 2012). For our paper we want to research the effect between the two results, to see whether it counts for using new technology in the financial sector, specifically the use of new technology for preventing money laundering or fraud. The current missing knowledge is that financial banks want to know if the positive attitude for new, technology because of perceived usefulness, also counts for their specific case where they have implemented artificial intelligence for preventing money laundering.

Relevance

The outcome of this research will deliver financial banks information if it is possible to implement AI on processes where customers have direct contact with AI. The case study is also valuable for financial banks because they can repeat the research for new technology. At last they can also use the results of the positive attitude of customers for marketing purposes.

RESEARCH QUESTION

Against this background the following leading research question of this research is:

What effect (positive versus negative) has preventing money laundering or fraud by new technology on its acceptance and does the use of private information affect this relation?

To answer this research question the following theoretical and practical research questions will be answered:

Theoretical research questions:

- What is money laundering or fraud within financial banks?
- Which private information does financial banks have of customers and why do they need this information?
- What is the relationship between private information and preventing money laundering or fraud?

Practical research questions:

- What effect has the use of private information on preventing money

laundering or fraud?

- How does the acceptance by customers of used technology benefit from the use of private information?

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The theoretical framework of this research will be explained below.

Conceptual model

To show the expected relationships between the different elements in our research question, we designed a conceptual model (figure 1). In our conceptual model we have distinguished the independent, quasi-moderating and dependent variable and followed by the relations (indicated with [H1 and H2](#)) between the variables. The conceptual model is used to visualize the concept of the research questions and its variables that influences the research. The dependent variable is composed from the research question. It combines the two primary subjects from the research question: The use of new technology and the acceptance of the new technology.

Figure 1 Conceptual model, the relationships between the dependent variable and the independent variable, with effect of a quasi-moderator.

Variable definition

The independent variable uses the subject's new technology, money laundering and fraud. Rotolo et al. (2015) defines new technology as an emerging technology and is stated as follows:

“a radically novel and relatively fast growing technology characterized by a certain degree of coherence persisting over time and with the potential to exert a considerable impact on the socio-economic domain(s) which is observed in terms of the composition of actors, institutions and patterns of interactions among those, along with the associated knowledge production processes. It's most prominent impact, however, lies in the future and so in the emergence phase is still somewhat uncertain and ambiguous (pp. 1827-1843)”.

Because AI is still defined as a trend (Gartner, 2019)

we correlate this to an emerging technology as stated above. The definition of money laundering and fraud belongs to the financial sector, in specific money laundering and fraud which happens in financial institutions. Zedlin (1998) defined money laundering as the process by which illicit money is made to appear licit. It is an essential element of any cash generating criminal venture. The manner in which money is laundered is limited only by the breadth of the imagination of the launderer. Fraud in financial institutions consist of two constitutes that are misstatements arising from fraudulent financial reporting and misstatements arising from misappropriation of assets. This was defined by the American institute of certified public accountants (ASB, 2002).

For the quasi moderator the subject private information will be used. We define private information as information that can be used to identify you, such as your social security number, street name, street address or zip code. Therefore, when 'private information' is mentioned in this paper, the private information financial banks can use to identify their customers is meant. The variable acceptance gets defined in the section research design.

Hypotheses

The hypotheses of this study are stated below.

H1: When a new technology gets implemented and is used for preventing money laundering and/or fraud, the acceptance of this new technology is positive.

H2: When a new technology for preventing money laundering or fraud has a relationship with the acceptance of this technology and uses private information for this, its acceptance is positive.

Explanation of the relationship of H1: Common known that the acceptance of new introduced and implemented technology is higher when the perceived usefulness by people is high. The study by Godoe and Johanson (2012) worked with a general research case. The researched correlation applies for new technology that are implemented for preventing money laundering or fraud within financial banks. First to research if there is a correlation between variables and if so, to see if this relation is positive or negative.

Explanation of the relationship of H2: The effect of the use of private information for preventing money laundering or fraud on its acceptance. If the test of hypotheses one results in a relationship with a positive or negative effect, we are going to research if the use of private information affects this relationship. If the technology uses private

information for preventing money laundering or fraud will it affect the effect it had on the acceptance level.

RESEARCH DESIGN

The research design of this study will be explained below.

Model

Research on positive or negative acceptances of new technology has already been performed. A model that is most used for measuring the acceptance of a new technology is the "Technology Acceptance Model" (Figure 2) (Davis, Bagozzia, & Warshaw, 1989). The technology acceptance model is considered one of the best frameworks to understand technology-related adoptions that can be extended and adapted to the different features of many diverse situations (Belanche, Casaló, & Flavián, 2012). For this research, a variant of the technology acceptance model is created (Figure 3) because the Dutch citizens are submitted to the technology, instead of adapting or using it in their daily lives (Marangunic & Granic, 2015). A few adjustments have been made to the technology acceptance model. The "perceived ease of use" and the "behavioral intention to use" are removed from the model. The "actual system use" is replaced by "level of acceptance". The level of acceptance is measured by the attitude towards the use of new technology for preventing money laundering or fraud. The attitude towards the use of new technology is influenced by the perceived usefulness. The perceived usefulness is determined by the external variables in this research: perceived risk, trust and use of private information (Wu & Wang, 2005). These external variables are defined in Table 1.

Figure 2 Original technology acceptance model (Davis, Bagozzia, & Warshaw, 1989)

Figure 3 Modified technology acceptance model. Adapted from original technology acceptance model (Davis, Bagozzia, & Warshaw, 1989).

Table 1 shows the variables of the modified technology acceptance model.

Table 1 Definitions of the variables in the modified technology acceptance model

Variable	Definition	Reference
Perceived Risk	The perceived uncertainty in a situation when technology use private information.	(Im, Kim, & Han, 2008)
Trust	Perceived trust indicates whether a person perceives that a particular new technological solution is secure and trustworthy or not.	(Dahlberg, Mallat, & Öörni, 2003)
Use of private information	Information that can be used to identify you, such as your social security number, street name, street address or zip code. That is used by technology.	See variable definition
Perceived usefulness	Perceived usefulness is the degree to which a person believes that the usage of a particular technology would be useful for them.	(Davis, Bagozzia, & Warshaw, 1989)
Attitude towards the use of new technology	The position towards the use of the new technology	(Davis, Bagozzia, & Warshaw, 1989)
Level of acceptance	The extent to which a new technology is accepted	See variable definition

Methods

The methods we used for the research will be

explained below.

Data collection

In this research two types of data collection are used to collect data about the acceptance of new technologies while using private information. Intermethod mixing results in the most accurate and complete information about the investigated subject (Tashakkori & Teddlie, 2002). This means that both quantitative as qualitative research will be mixed within this study. Therefore, the methods interviews and questionnaires are used to collect data with two different methods. First of all, an interview is conducted with an expert among computer science. The main objectives of this interview are to gain new information. Secondly, we are collecting data through online questionnaires. These questionnaires focus on the opinion of the customers of ABN Amro towards the acceptance of AI to prevent money laundering or fraud and if the use of private information affect this relationship, and if private information has a direct effect on the acceptance. This online questionnaire is electronically distributed by placing this questionnaire on Facebook and LinkedIn. By using this method we can target the most people in the sample within in our time and budget limit. The problem of an online questionnaire is the impossibility of a calculation of the response rate (van Selm & Jankowski, 2006). However, to increase the response rate several actions are used. These actions are: maximizing trust trough ensuring anonymity and clear communication about this research, ensuring that time and effort of the customer is minimized and showing appreciation of through thanking the participant and friendly language.

Survey research

We use survey research as research design to measure the level of acceptance by Dutch citizens towards new technology. There has been chosen for surveys since personal opinions and attitudes of citizens are needed for analyzing and according to Isaac and Michael (1995) survey research is most used for these cases. Moreover, a survey research uses a selected proportion of a population that can be generalized to a population (Kraemer, 1991). Kraemer (1991) also stated that the data from survey research is subjective, which is necessary in this research. Surveys are useful to obtain information from a large population like Dutch citizens. Because it is impossible to measure the whole population of Dutch customers who are using financial banking more than once a month, a survey research will give a sample that can be generalized back to the population (Glasow, 2005) In order to perform a survey research, several decisions must be made. First the operationalization of concepts must be

determined. Then needs to be decided which survey mode will be used and how the questionnaire will be formulated. Eventually decisions will be made on how, what, when and how much data will be collected (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016).

The survey structure is based on an earlier study from Wu & Wang (2005). Therefore, the structure is tested and reliable for this case, since it is a comparable case (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016). The survey questionnaire consists of two parts. In the first part the respondent's demographic information is registered. In the second part the respondent's perception of each variable in the technology acceptance model is asked. The demographic variables assessed based on the earlier study of Wu & Wang (2005) were: gender, age, level of education and income level. The second part questioned each respondent to indicate each level of agreement with each variable in the technology acceptance model (Wu & Wang, 2005). The survey exist of closed-ended and open-ended questions. Closed-ended questions are asked to the respondents to make choices among a set of alternatives. The advantages of closed-ended questions is that it helps respondents to make quick decisions. The scale of the questions consists of an off-the-shelf scale. The advantages of this scale that it is tested, reliable and valid for the specific case (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016). The survey contained a five point Likert-type-scale, where 1 indicates strongly disagree, 2 indicates disagree, 3 stand for neutral, 4 indicates for agree and 5 indicates strongly agree (Albaum, 1997). Besides the closed-ended question the survey contained two open-ended questions that challenge respondents to give an opinion about the topics.

The results of the interview are qualitative. The questions of survey about the variables came from a related study about a digital environment (Liaw & Huang, 2013). Because computer science is aligned with AI and other new technology, the same variables are useful for our study. For the variable 'trust', the satisfaction is measured and for the variables perceived risk and usefulness the believe and intend are measured. The other variables are linked to their own definition. For related open-ended survey questions we used AI specific questions for perceived usefulness (Danysz, et al., 2019). The answers to the questions are going to be summarized: the questions and the aggregates of the answers are described in [appendix A](#) and [appendix B](#). The demographic questions are not included in the appendix because of privacy regulations.

Multiple variables are involved in the survey. To measure the reliability of the survey Cronbach's alpha is used. Cronbach's alpha can check whether the set of variables are interrelated (Gliem & Gliem, 2003). According to Tavakol and Dennick (2011), an acceptable range of the value should be between 0.70 and 0.90 to get a high degree of internal consistency.

Sampling process

To make sure the survey research is useful, a sampling process is set up to understand how the survey research should be done for this research. First of all, the population of this research are the financial bank customers of three biggest banks in the Netherlands. That are the customers of ABN AMRO, Rabobank and ING Bank according to Business Insider (2019). For our case study, only the customers of ABN AMRO are considered as sampling frame. Moreover, the sampling design of this research is the probability sampling simple random sampling. This method is chosen, because of the need of representativeness and high generalizability of findings to the entire population. Simple random sampling has this advantage and has the least bias (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016). Furthermore, the sample size is determined between 75 and 500 responses. According to Roscoe (1975), this is appropriate for most research. The objective is to get as many responses as possible, because this will reduce standard error. However, over 500 responses is considered as problematic because it will take too much time and the possibility of committing type II errors.

Pre-test with expert

Before primary data collection, a survey with an expert in the field of computer sciences is used to pre-test the questionnaire. This pre-test is performed to gather the base assessing information before the main survey is fulfilled. The results of the pre-test will be compared to the results of the sample to test the knowledge gap between the expert and novices (Horst, Kuttschreuter, & Gutteling, 2007). The expert has filled in the same survey as held for data collection with the Dutch citizens (Lichtenthaler, 2019). The expert that is used for the pre-test is a PhD assistant professor in the sector of computer science. Because of time restraints, a sample size of one is used for the pre-test questionnaire.

Interview with expert

To answer the practical research questions, an interview with an expert with the subject of AI is held. This expert is an employee of a Dutch bank who is specialized with AI and bank transactions. This interview is held to get knowledge from an expert in the field of AI within banks. This information will be compared with the output of the survey.

RESULTS

Firstly, the results of the pre-test with the computer science expert are stated below. The expert agreed with the survey and could answer all answers except for one question. This was an open-ended question which was vague according to him. Because of the

vagueness of this question, it was decided to not include this question in the survey.

The main results of the questionnaires are as follows: This survey had thirteen respondents and a Cronbach's Alpha of 0.8870. The majority, 69.2 %, of the respondents have heard of AI before participating in this survey, 53.8 percent of the respondents had a neutral opinion about the hypothesis: "I am satisfied with financial institutes using AI". To the hypothesis: "I am satisfied with financial institutes using AI as a tool for preventing money laundering or fraud", 61.5 % of the respondents strongly agreed and 30.8% agreed as well on this hypothesis. Furthermore, 53.8 % disagreed to the hypothesis "I find it useful if AI from financial institutes uses my private information". Then, the majority of the respondents, 53.8%, have a neutral opinion to the statement: "I believe using AI while using my private information is an effective tool for financial institutes". Finally, 46.2 % strongly agreed and 46.2% agreed with the hypothesis: "I am satisfied with financial institutes using my private information for AI as a tool for preventing money laundering or fraud".

Unfortunately through unexpected circumstances, the interview was cancelled by the expert. Through time limitations there was not enough time to arrange a new interview with another expert.

CONCLUSION

To refer back to the problem statement, the goal of this research is to identify the acceptance of Dutch citizens for a new technology. The results of the case study, which used the use of artificial intelligence on preventing money laundering or fraud within financial banks gave some interesting insights. An interesting result of the survey is the relationship between the use of private information for preventing money laundering or fraud and the acceptance. The survey asked for the perceived usefulness of the respondents towards financial institutes using AI in combination with private information. The majority of the respondents, 53.8%, had a neutral opinion. We ask this question again, but added a new section to the question, "preventing money laundering or fraud". 46.2 % strongly agreed and 46.2% agreed with this question. Based on this outcome, we carefully conclude that the acceptance of AI using private information for preventing money laundering or fraud has a positive effect. This should be considered when financial institutes definitive introduce new technology. The results of the research supported the hypotheses, [H1 and H2](#), as stated in this paper.

DISCUSSION

The technology acceptance model that was created, had three external variables. In reality, there are extraneous variables that may affect the acceptance and which we did not include in this research, which is a limitation of this research. However, the model would have become too complex because of the limitations in time. Our sampling had some limitations as well. First, by placing the questionnaire on Facebook and LinkedIn, the sample consists of people from our own network. Besides, the survey had thirteen responses, this is not close to our sample size. In addition, we did not only use the results of ABN Amro because of the small sampling size. Therefore, we have used the results of all the three Dutch banks to make it as generalizable as possible. Thus, the results may not be fully generalizable. However, if the conceptual model is followed, the research question and hypothesis can be answered properly. For further research on this topic, it is required to describe more external variables. This way the research is more specific and the results become more reliable. Also, it is suggested to repeat the survey process on a larger scale to get a better view of the opinion of the sample. Lastly, in further research, an interview with an expert of AI who works at a Dutch bank should be done.

Response to the feedback.

The feedback from the three "anonymous" reviewers was very valuable for the paper. With the feedback we have been able to improve our paper qualitatively.

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APPENDIX A

Closed-ended questionnaire survey

Perceived satisfaction	SAT01	I am satisfied with AI as an assisted financial tool.
	SAT02	I am satisfied with using AI functions within financial banks.
	SAT03	I am satisfied with learning AI for financial activities.
	SAT04	I am satisfied with financial banks using AI.
	SAT05	I am satisfied with financial banks using AI as a tool for preventing money laundering or fraud.

Perceived usefulness	USE01	I believe AI systems is a useful financial tool.
	USE02	I believe using AI is effective tool for financial banks.
	USE03	I intend to use AI to assist my financial activities in the future.
	USE04	I intend to use AI for my financial activities.
	USE05	I believe AI systems are a useful tool for preventing money laundering or fraud.

Use of private information	PRI01	I am satisfied with AI from financial banks using my private information.
	PRI02	I find it useful if AI from financial banks uses my private information.
	PRI03	I am satisfied with financial banks using my private information for AI.
	PRI04	I believe using AI while using my private information is effective tool for financial banks.
	PRI05	I am satisfied with financial banks using my private information for AI as a tool for preventing money laundering or fraud.
	PRI06	I believe AI while using my private information systems are a useful tool for preventing money laundering or fraud.

APPENDIX B

Open-ended questionnaire survey

How would you like your role to adapt to the future where AI-assisted technology augments how you do your work?
What skills and competencies would you like to develop or learn in order to perform your financial activities in the future where AI assists you to do your work?